

Lost Pet Identification and Shelter Matching Using Image Recognition

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Abstract- The major aim of this study is the investigation and acquisition of important data from a huge dataset, notably in the realm of discovering lost pets in animal shelters. The primary purpose is to employ convolutional neural networks and the MobileNet approach to assess the present dataset, which comprises photos of different missing pet breeds. The study's goal is to raise awareness of the treatment's applicability and its influence on the reunion of lost dogs and their owners. This research emphasizes the usage of new technique to increase the potential of Finding lost pets and reuniting them with their giving hope to owners of pets and their families' dear buddies.

Keywords: CNN Algorithm, MobileNetV2, image Recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of finding and reuniting missing animals with their rightful owners is known as "lost pet identification". The issue of pets going missing has gained increasing attention in recent years due to the increase in pet ownership and the importance of pets in people's lives. Since losing a pet can be stressful for the owner, it is important to reunite pet owners with their beloved animals. In order to overcome the difficulties of lost pet identification, this study uses convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a well-known type of artificial neural networks. CNNs have proven to be effective in a variety of image processing tasks, such as segmentation, object identification, and picture categorization.

Convolution is a mathematical procedure that uses filters to produce feature maps that emphasize important patterns in the input picture, and it is used to automatically extract features from images. CNNs are specifically designed for this purpose. CNNs learn about the numerical values included in these filters as part of the training process. In order to match lost pet photographs with prospective shelter counterparts and eventually assist in reuniting missing pets with their owners, this project will make use of CNNs' MobileNet algorithm for the analysis of lost pet images.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] The use of deep learning techniques for pet identification is examined in E. Azizi's study "Deep Learning Pet Recognition Using Facial and Body" from 2023.

This study addresses the issue of lost pet recognition at animal shelters by providing insights into methods for recognizing pets based on their facial and physical characteristics.

[2] The research that S.B. Islam conducted in 2023 on "Animal Species Recognition with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks" is relevant to your study. In the context of misplaced pet identification, it addresses deep learning techniques for species categorization that may be modified to identify different pet breeds.

The study conducted in 2023 by H.Y. Chen, titled "Convolutional Neural Network-Based Automated System for Dog Emotion Recognition," provides evidence of the use of convolutional neural networks for the identification and categorization of canine emotions. The usage of CNNs for dogs is pertinent to your work even if the focus is on emotions.

A 2020 study by K. Lai titled "Dog Identification using Soft Biometrics and Neural Networks" explores the application of soft biometrics in dog identification. This strategy may improve your research's methodology by offering insights into pet identification utilizing distinctive traits like soft biometrics.

[1] E. Azizi's 2023 paper offers a thorough framework for deep learning-based pet identification, highlighting the significance of precise species categorization in helping owners find their missing pets.

[4] The idea of soft biometrics for pet identification is presented in K. Lai's 2020 article, "Dog Identification using Soft Biometrics and Neural Networks". This creative method raises the possibility of using characteristics more than only physical characteristics to improve pet identification accuracy when they go missing.

The realms of animal care and pet ownership place a high

importance on the accurate and efficient detection of missing pets. The manual searches and descriptions used in the more antiquated techniques of identifying missing pets are frequently laborious and prone to mistakes. On the other hand, the process of finding missing dogs and their owners may be completely transformed by using cutting edge machine learning techniques.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been at the forefront of image identification technology in recent years, demonstrating their versatility and increasing in popularity across a wide range of applications. For the purposes of this research, the goal is to use picture recognition technology to help quickly and accurately identify dogs who have gone missing based just on their appearance.

III. METHODOLOGY

Several crucial phases are included in the process for picture detection of missing pets using the MobileNet algorithm:

Data Preparation: A wide range of pet breeds and types should be included in the collection of missing pet photos. Divide the dataset into two subsets: a testing set to assess performance and a training set to train the model.

Model Training: For image recognition, select the MobileNet algorithm as the neural network architecture. Sort comparable photographs into separate divisions according to pet breeds or species. Utilizing the training dataset, instruct the MobileNet model to identify the unique characteristics of every pet breed.

Model Evaluation: Analyze the model's effectiveness with the testing dataset. In order to assess how well the model classifies missing pet photos, measure important performance measures such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

Image Recognition: Use the MobileNet model that has been trained to recognize images in real time. Give consumers the option to share pictures of their missing pets so that the model can identify the breed or species from whence they came.

User interface: Provide an intuitive online application for identifying lost pet images. Use the trained MobileNet model by implementing the recognition logic in the web application.

Continuous Improvement: To get user input, incorporate a feedback feature within the web application. To improve the model's identification ability, add new

photos of missing pets to the dataset on a regular basis.

This technique describes how to use the MobileNet algorithm to train, test, and implement a picture identification system for missing dogs, which will eventually help the pets and their owners reunite.

IV. BUILD MODEL

Using the MobileNet method, the following procedures are carried out in order to develop a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful image detection of missing pets:

Importing libraries

```
1 import os
2 import tensorflow as tf
3 import numpy as np
4 from flask import Flask, request, jsonify, render_template_string, send_from_directory
5 from flask_cors import CORS
6 from werkzeug.utils import secure_filename
7 from PIL import Image
8 model = tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2(weights='imagenet')
9
```

Fig.1: importing libraries

MobileNetV2: A particular kind of neural network architecture called MobileNetV2 is intended for embedded and mobile applications. With its small size and high efficiency, this neural network can function even on mobile devices like smartphones that have little processing power. This neural network design, which is useful for tasks like object identification and picture categorization, is probably implemented in the "mobilenetv2" module.

TensorFlow (TF): Google created the open-source machine learning framework TensorFlow (TF). It is intended to create, train, and implement different machine learning models—including neural networks—for a variety of uses, including speech recognition, computer vision, and natural language processing. A wide range of tools and libraries are available with TensorFlow to help develop and optimize machine learning models and run them effectively on PCs, servers, and mobile devices.

OS module gives you access to the computer's operating system that Python is executing on. It has several tools and ways to do things like going through folders, making and removing files and folders, finding system information, and controlling environment variables.

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Flask: It is a micro web framework for Python that enables programmers to create web apps with little effort and speed. It is intended to be simple to use, flexible, and lightweight. Flask gives developers the freedom to select and include additional components as needed, while still offering the fundamentals for building online applications, such routing, request processing, and template rendering.

Training the Model

```

18 def preprocess_image(image_path):
19     img = tf.keras.preprocessing.image.load_img(image_path, target_size=(224, 224))
20     img = tf.keras.preprocessing.image.img_to_array(img)
21     img = tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.preprocess_input(img)
22     img = np.expand_dims(img, axis=0)
23     return img
24
25
26 def classify_image(image_path):
27     image = preprocess_image(image_path)
28     predictions = model.predict(image)
29     decoded_predictions = tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.decode_predictions(predictions, top=5)[0]
30     return decoded_predictions
31
32
33 def compare_classifications(user_image_path, shelter_image_path):
34     user_predictions = classify_image(user_image_path)
35     shelter_predictions = classify_image(shelter_image_path)
36
37     user_labels = set([label for label, _, _ in user_predictions])
38     shelter_labels = set([label for label, _, _ in shelter_predictions])
39
40     match = bool(user_labels.intersection(shelter_labels))
41
42     return match
    
```

Fig.2: Training and Classification

```

@app.route('/analyze', methods=['POST'])
def analyze_image():
    if 'user_image' not in request.files:
        return jsonify({"error": "No image uploaded"}), 400

    user_image = request.files['user_image']
    if user_image.filename == '':
        return jsonify({"error": "Invalid image filename"}), 400

    filename = secure_filename(user_image.filename)
    user_image_path = os.path.join(upload_folder, filename)
    user_image.save(user_image_path)

    matched_breed = "Unknown"
    matched_shelter_image = None

    for shelter_filename in os.listdir(shelter_folder):
        shelter_image_path = os.path.join(shelter_folder, shelter_filename)
        match = compare_classifications(user_image_path, shelter_image_path)
        if match:
            matched_breed = classify_image(user_image_path)
            matched_shelter_image = shelter_filename
            break

    if matched_breed == "Unknown":
        matched_breed = classify_image(user_image_path)

    matched_breed = [{"label": label, 'breed': breed, 'confidence': float(confidence)} for label, breed, confidence in matched_breed]

    response_data = {
        'result': 'match' if matched_shelter_image else 'no_match',
        'matched_breed': matched_breed,
        'matched_shelter_image': matched_shelter_image
    }
    
```

Fig.3: Analyze

VI. RESULT

Fig.4: Result matching with shelter Database

VII. CONCLUSION

Accurate projections have been produced when the MobileNet algorithm has been used to identify missing dogs from photos. The systematic steps in this approach's procedure include collecting many datasets of images of missing dogs, preparing the data, training the model, evaluating the model's performance, and projecting the result. Together, these methods increase the precision and speed of missing pet identification.

There are a number of advantages to using this process, including a significant reduction in the time and cost required to analyze each provided image and generate accurate projections. It is a helpful tool for both pet owners and animal shelters since it is designed to be simple to use and comprehensible by those with little expertise.

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